

The Leaf-Shaped Frenectomy: A Minimal-Invasive Design – A Case Report

Abstract:

Aesthetic and functional concerns in dentistry have led to a growing focus on managing anatomical anomalies like high frenal attachments, which can compromise oral health and smile aesthetics. High labial frenum attachment, especially of the papilla-penetrating type, is often associated with challenges such as midline diastema, gingival recession, impaired oral hygiene, and speech difficulties. This case report highlights the use of a minimally invasive "leaf-shaped frenectomy" technique as a novel approach to address such concerns.

This report emphasizes the advantages of the leaf-shaped frenectomy technique, including aesthetic precision, reduced postoperative complications, and compatibility with orthodontic treatment. The multidisciplinary approach ensured seamless integration with orthodontic care, highlighting the importance of collaboration in achieving optimal functional and aesthetic outcomes. This minimally invasive method aligns with contemporary demands for advanced, patient-centred dental solutions.

Introduction:

Aesthetic concerns in dentistry have gained immense significance in recent years as patients increasingly seek treatments that not only restore function but also enhance appearance. The harmonious interplay of teeth, gums, and lips plays a vital role in achieving an attractive smile. As a result, the focus has shifted toward managing soft and hard tissue abnormalities that disrupt this balance. Among these concerns, a high frenal attachment often stands out as a factor that can compromise both aesthetics and function, necessitating its removal through surgical interventions like frenectomy.⁽¹⁾

The labial frenum is a thin fold of mucosal tissue that connects the lip to the alveolar mucosa, gingiva, or underlying periosteum. In some individuals, the frenum is abnormally positioned, extending close to or into the gingival margin.⁽²⁾ This condition, referred to as high frenum attachment, is often associated with aesthetic and functional challenges. A prominent or aberrantly positioned frenum can lead to midline diastema, impaired lip mobility, compromised oral hygiene, and speech difficulties. Additionally, it may contribute to gingival recession by exerting tension on the attached gingiva, further complicating the periodontal condition.

From an aesthetic perspective, a high frenum attachment can significantly disrupt the smile line and the symmetry of the anterior dentition. The presence of a midline diastema, a gap between the central incisors, is one of the most common aesthetic concerns associated with this anomaly⁽³⁾. While this condition is often perceived as unappealing, it can also undermine the psychological well-being of individuals, affecting their confidence and self-esteem. In such cases, managing the high frenum attachment becomes essential to restore both function and aesthetics.

The need for frenectomy, a surgical procedure to remove or modify the frenal attachment, arises when the frenum interferes with oral health or aesthetics⁽⁴⁾. Frenectomy can be performed using traditional scalpel techniques⁽⁵⁾, electrosurgery, or lasers, depending on the

case requirements and the clinician's expertise. Each technique has its advantages, with laser-assisted procedures offering reduced bleeding, minimal postoperative discomfort, and faster healing. The choice of technique often depends on the extent of the problem and the desired aesthetic outcome.

In cases where the high frenum attachment compromises gingival health, frenectomy plays a dual role in aesthetics and disease prevention.⁽⁶⁾ The removal of the aberrant frenum eliminates the tension on the gingiva, reducing the risk of recession and improving periodontal stability. Furthermore, the procedure facilitates orthodontic closure of the midline diastema, contributing to a more harmonious and pleasing dental appearance.⁽⁷⁾

Recent advances in surgical techniques, such as the leaf-shaped frenectomy, have further refined the approach to treating high frenum attachments. These techniques focus on achieving optimal functional and aesthetic results with minimal tissue trauma. By preserving the integrity of surrounding structures and promoting rapid healing, such innovative approaches align with the growing demand for minimally invasive and cosmetically appealing solutions in dentistry.

This case report highlights the significance of addressing high frenum attachment as part of aesthetic and functional dental care. It underscores the importance of meticulous diagnosis, patient-centred treatment planning, and the role of advanced surgical techniques in delivering predictable and aesthetically superior outcomes.

Case report:

This clinical case was performed in the department of periodontology. The patient aged 27 years was referred from the département of orthodontics with the chief complaint of high labial frenum. On intraoral examination the papilla penetrating type of frenal attachment was seen, a positive pull test indicated tension on the gingiva. The surrounding gingiva showed no significant inflammation. The details of leaf shaped frenectomy using scalpel procedure were explained verbally to the patient. Patient signed the informed consent. Patient was evaluated by clinical examinations and documented by digital photos and patient was prepared for the surgery. Complete blood count (CBC), bleeding time, clotting time, viral screens (HBsAG, HCV and HIV) was requested.

The armamentarium consisted of a haemostat, scalpel blade no. 15, gauze sponges, 4-0 black silk sutures, suture pliers, scissors. Following this, the area was anesthetized using local infiltration with 2% lignocaine containing 1:80,000 adrenaline. For the leaf shaped labial frenectomy the upper lip was pulled upward by the assistant hands and then the frenum was tightened. (Figure 1)

Figure 1: Pre operative image

The haemostat was positioned on the frenum, and instead of making sharp cuts along its margins, a circular incision was made. This circular approach gave the excised frenum a leaf-like shape. (Figure 2)

Figure 2: Leaf shaped frenum incision

The frenum was repositioned to an apical location and secured using silk sutures. (Figure 3) The frenum's leaf-shaped structure and rounded edges helped minimize tension during suturing, eliminating the need for additional releasing incisions at the corners. This approach facilitated uneventful healing observed at the 1-month follow-up. (Figure 4)

Figure 3: Suturing after frenectomy

Figure 4: One month follow up healing

Discussion:

High frenum attachment is a common anatomical variation that can interfere with orthodontic treatment by preventing diastema closure or causing relapse. Frenectomy plays a critical role in eliminating these challenges⁽³⁾. The leaf-shaped frenectomy technique is particularly advantageous in cases requiring aesthetic precision and minimal postoperative complications.

This approach allows for precise tissue excision while preserving adjacent structures, making it suitable for patients in the mid-phase of orthodontic treatment. Unlike traditional techniques⁽⁸⁾, the leaf-shaped design promotes rapid healing, reduces the risk of scarring, and ensures a functional outcome that complements orthodontic therapy.

In this case, the multidisciplinary collaboration between the orthodontist and periodontist was pivotal. The timely removal of the high frenum attachment facilitated uninterrupted orthodontic progress and contributed to achieving the desired aesthetic and functional goals.⁽⁹⁾

Conclusion:

This case highlights the importance of addressing high frenum attachments in orthodontic patients through minimally invasive techniques like the leaf-shaped frenectomy. The procedure not only enhances the effectiveness of orthodontic treatment but also ensures optimal aesthetic and functional outcomes. A multidisciplinary approach, coupled with meticulous surgical planning, is key to managing such cases successfully.

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